

Ferrisalicylate and Sulphosalicylate Complexes in Dioxane Water Mixtures

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The equilibrium constants for the complexes

in dioxane water mixtures containing 20%, 45%, 70% and 82% dioxane by weight and other thermodynamic parameters in 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane, have been determined. Attempt has been made to explain the role of solvent on equilibrium processes.

With a view to ascertain the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes, we studied the dissociation constants of the complexes in mixed solvents (dioxane water) containing 20%, 45%, 70% and 82% of dioxane by weight and also other thermodynamic parameters in solutions having 70% and 82% by weight of dioxane spectrophotometrically. We report in this communication the results of the investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric perchlorate was prepared and estimated as also total acid in ferric perchlorate, in the way described before¹. Salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid were of E. Merck's reagent grade and estimated in the usual way. Dioxane was purified as described before². Ferric salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid complexes³ in water absorb strongly in the visible region. In order to observe the effect of solvent on the complex, we have run the spectra of a number of solutions containing the same amount of ferric ion, ligand and perchloric acid but differing only in the percentage of organic solvent (0-82%). Though the nature of the spectrum does not change with organic solvent, the optical density decreases with increasing percentage of organic solvent. In medium with high percentages of organic solvent, the ligands are very little dissociated as the dielectric constant becomes lower and lower and as a result, the concentration of the complex becomes smaller and smaller, thus accounting for the decrease in the optical density. The composition of the complexes of ferric salicylic acid and ferric sulphosalicylic acid are known to be 1 : 1 at low *pH*s in aqueous solutions. This has been found to be true by Job's method of continuous variation in mixed solvents also. (Wavelengths of measurements were 490, 500 and 510 m μ).

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1. U. C. Bhattacharyya *et al.* *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46** 497.
2. S. K. Pal, *et al.*, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 497.
3. A. Agren, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 226, 1059; 1955, **9**, 49.

The molar extinction coefficients of the complexes were determined from the measurement of o.d.'s of solutions containing 50 to 100 fold excess of ligand. The constancy of the o.d. readings also suggests that under this condition only one complex is formed. The mean molar extinction coefficient values are :

For ferric-salicylate	for ferric-sulphosalicylate
$\epsilon_{490m\mu} = 1432 \pm 3$	$\epsilon_{490m\mu} = 1865 \pm 4$
$\epsilon_{500m\mu} = 1542 \pm 4$	$\epsilon_{500m\mu} = 1948 \pm 5$
$\epsilon_{510m\mu} = 1618 \pm 4$	$\epsilon_{510m\mu} = 1993 \pm 5$

The extinction coefficient values were found to be same in aqueous and mixed solvents.

To calculate the stability constant of the complexes by spectrophotometric method, a series of solutions containing $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ and ligands of different concentrations were prepared. In case of solutions containing 20% and 45% of dioxane by weight, measurements were taken at 25° whereas in case of solutions containing 70% and 82% of dioxane by weight, measurements were taken at 15°, 25° and 35° at three wavelengths 490, 500 and 510 $m\mu$ s. Measurements were taken with Beckmann D.U. spectrophotometer fitted with thermostatic device.

RESULTS

Since the complex formations between ferric ion and ligands take place in the ratio 1 : 1, the reaction can be written as :—

The equilibrium constants for the reactions are

$$K_{T_{\text{Fe-Sal}}} = K_c \times \frac{f_{\text{FeA}^+}}{f_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}} \quad \dots (3)$$

and

$$K_{T_{\text{FeSulosal}}} = K_c \times \frac{f_{\text{H}^+}}{f_{\text{Fe}^{3+}} \times f_{\text{HA}^-}} \quad \dots (4)$$

For the calculation of the equilibrium constants the concentration of the complex has been determined from optical density and extinction coefficient values. The concentration of free ferric ion is determined from the relationship.

$$[\text{Fe}^{3+}]_{\text{Total}} = [\text{Fe}^{3+}]_{\text{free}} + [\text{Complex}] \quad \dots (5)$$

The concentration of free hydrogen ion is taken equal to the amount of free perchloric acid present in the solution. In the calculation, the contribution of H^+ ion due to the reaction is neglected as the concentrations of the ligands are very small and much of the ligands are present as such in the experimental solutions. $[\text{HA}^-]_{\text{Sal}}$ and $[\text{HA}^-]_{\text{Sulosal}}$ have been calculated in the usual way from the dissociation constants of the ligands and their total concentrations.

The ionic strengths of the solution are of the order of $4-5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in case of ferric salicylate complex and $4-8 \times 10^{-3}M$ in case of sulphosalicylate complex. The values of K_1 of salicylic acids and K_2 of sulphosalicylic acids at these ionic strengths were calculated using our values given before².

The values of equilibrium constants for the reactions (1) and (2) are given in Table I.

TABLE 1

Reaction	Temp. °C	percentage of organic solvent	Equilibrium constant K_e
$Fe^{3+} + HA^- \rightleftharpoons FeA^+ + H^+$ ($A^- =$ Salicylate ion)	25	20	$1.75(\pm 0.96) \times 10^3$
	25	45	$1.65(\pm 0.06) \times 10^4$
	15	70	$1.13(\pm 0.10) \times 10^6$
	25	70	$5.46(\pm 0.10) \times 10^5$
	35	70	$3.22(\pm 0.20) \times 10^5$
	15	82	$5.54(\pm 0.20) \times 10^7$
	25	82	$2.45(\pm 0.20) \times 10^7$
	35	82	$1.18(\pm 0.20) \times 10^7$
	$Fe^{3+} + HA^= \rightleftharpoons FeA + H^+$ ($A^= =$ Sulphosalicylate ion)	25	20
25		45	$2.82(\pm 0.20) \times 10^4$
15		70	$1.05(\pm 0.20) \times 10^6$
25		70	$0.71(\pm 0.05) \times 10^6$
35		70	$0.47(\pm 0.05) \times 10^6$
15		82	$8.50(\pm 0.30) \times 10^6$
25		82	$3.61(\pm 0.20) \times 10^6$
35		82	$1.87(\pm 0.20) \times 10^6$

Other thermodynamic properties have been determined from the equilibrium constant values at three different temperatures in the same way described before¹. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Temp = 25°				
Reaction	% of dioxane	ΔG in Kcal/mole	ΔH in Kcal/mole	ΔS cal/deg.
$Fe^{3+} + HA^- \rightleftharpoons FeA^+ + H^+$ ($A^- =$ Salicylate ion)	20	-4.42	—	—
	45	-5.75	—	—
	70	-7.82	-11.17	-11.2
	82	-9.94	-13.93	-13.3
$Fe^{3+} + HA^= \rightleftharpoons FeA + H^+$ ($A^= =$ Sulphosalicylate ion)	20	-4.70	—	—
	45	-6.07	—	—
	70	-7.98	-7.17	+2.7
	82	-8.94	-12.30	-11.3

DISCUSSION

The pK values for the reaction $Fe^{3+} + HA^- \rightleftharpoons FeA^+ + H^+$ (Ferric salicylate complex) at 25° are -3.23 (20% dioxane by wt.), -4.22 (45% dioxane by weight), -5.74 (70%) and

-7.39 (82%) whereas for $\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA} + \text{H}^+$ (Ferric sulphosalicylate complex) the corresponding values are -3.45 , -4.45 , -5.85 and -6.56 respectively.

The comparison of the present result with others is not possible due to the lack of data in the literature. The second (in case of salicylate complex) and third (in case of sulphosalicylate complex) dissociation constants of the ligands are not known at these high percentages of organic solvent. So it is very difficult to predict quantitatively to what extent the stability of the complexes are affected by the solvent. A qualitative explanation may be attempted. Van Uitert *et al.*⁴ reported a value of 3.16×10^{-16} for the second dissociation constant of salicylic acid in dioxane water mixture containing 75% dioxane by weight at 30° . Taking the second dissociation constant of salicylic acid to be equal to 3.16×10^{-16} in 70% as well as 82% dioxane by weight in mixed solvents at 25° , the formation constants for the reaction $\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{A}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}^+$ at these percentages of organic solvents come out to be of the order of $\sim 10^{21}$ and $\sim 10^{23}$ whereas the formation constant value in aqueous solution is 6.6×10^{15} . No such values could be obtained for sulphosalicylate complexes ($\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{A}^{3-} \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}$) as the third dissociation constants in organic solvents are not available.

We find here the neutralisation of charges involving trivalent and bivalent ions, thus dielectric constant should affect the stability of the complex to a large extent. It is not possible to say definitely how and to what extent the acid-base property affects the stability of the complex.

If the free energy change associated with the equilibrium process is taken as

$$\Delta G = \Delta G_{el} + \Delta G_{\text{nonelect}}$$

then we have

$$-\log K = \frac{a}{D} + \frac{\Delta G_{\text{nonelect}}}{2.303 RT} \quad \left(\text{as } \Delta G_{el} = \frac{Ne^2}{2 rD} \right)$$

We have noted straight line relationships when $-\log K$ was plotted against $1/D$ (upto $D = 30$) or mole-fraction of the organic solvent for the reactions $\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA} + \text{H}^+$ (with proper charges) similar to that observed in case of ligands². For the reaction in water, we have calculated the value from Agren's³ data in $3M$ NaClO_4 .

Agren³ noted a parallelism between $\log K_{\text{form}}$ of the complexes ($\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{A}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}$) with $\log K_{\text{Phenolic}}$ group in aqueous solutions. For the reaction $\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA} + \text{H}^+$, the values of K should be the same irrespective of the ligand. The values for the reactions calculated from Agren's data are 5.01×10^2 and 4.8×10^2 for ferric salicylate and sulphosalicylate complexes respectively in $3M$ - NaClO_4 at 25° in aqueous solutions. We note the same trend in mixed solvents. A slight discrepancy in the case of sulphosalicylate complex may be due to the evaluation of free HA^- where sulphonic acid group is assumed to be completely dissociated which may not be the case particularly in mixed solvents where dielectric constant is low.

Analysis of the thermodynamic data of the complexes are difficult. It is reasonable to assume that the dissociation of the complexes should be more and more endothermic as the dioxane concentration increases which is actually observed in practice.

According to Latimer and Jolly⁵, entropy change results from (1) displacement process i.e., displacement of solvent molecules from the co-ordination sphere and (2) charge effect.

It is extremely difficult to find out the separate contributions in mixed solvents particularly at higher percentages of organic solvents. In high percentages of the organic solvents, it is not known to what extent Fe^{3+} ion and H^+ ions are solvated i.e., whether the co-ordination zone of Fe^{3+} ion is occupied and H^+ ion is solvated by water molecules or by dioxane molecules or by both. In case of reactions (1) and (2) neutralisation of higher charges are involved and entropy change should be favourable. From this consideration entropy change in case of sulphosalicylic acid complex should be more favourable. Qualitatively, it has been found to be true.

The anomaly in mixed solvents must be due to solvational properties (ion-solvent interaction and solvent-solvent interactions) and displacement processes. Extensive thermodynamic studies in mixed solvents are needed to understand the role of different thermodynamic parameters in complex formation in mixed solvents.

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